

Lab tips, tricks and hacks:

Improved humidity control for gloveless anaerobic chambers in the deterministic transfer of air-sensitive 2D materials

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Introduction and context

In our earlier work published in *2D Materials* ([Patricia Gant et al 2020 2D Mater. 7 025034](#)), we described a cost-effective and modular setup for the deterministic transfer of 2D materials in inert environmental conditions. This setup relied on a [gloveless anaerobic chamber](#), originally designed for biological research, to provide an oxygen- and moisture-free atmosphere suitable for the manipulation of highly air-sensitive materials such as black phosphorus and certain halide perovskites. Our approach significantly lowered the entry barrier for laboratories aiming to handle air-sensitive 2D materials, offering a low-cost alternative to traditional gloveboxes. One of the key advantages of this system is that it enables direct manipulation with bare hands inside the anaerobic chamber—unlike standard materials science gloveboxes, which rely on thick, cumbersome gloves. This freedom greatly facilitates delicate tasks such as exfoliating flakes, operating tweezers, and precisely adjusting micromanipulator stages, providing a level of dexterity and control that is otherwise difficult to achieve.

Motivation for improvement

Although the gloveless anaerobic chamber proved successful in maintaining low oxygen levels, its original design presents a limitation for materials science applications: humidity control. These chambers often include an internal pressure regulator that stabilizes internal pressure during arm movements by allowing gas to flow through a liquid-based bubbler. While this design is

effective for biological cultures, it introduces persistent moisture into the system, making it difficult to maintain relative humidity (RH) levels below ~10% — a critical threshold for many air-sensitive materials. Although successive nitrogen purging cycles can temporarily reduce RH down to even 2%, it quickly rises again during routine operation.

Description of the improvement

To address this issue, we developed and implemented a simple yet highly effective method to control humidity inside the chamber, enabling consistent operation at RH levels as low as 3% even while in active use:

1. **Recirculating molecular sieve cartridge:** We built a cartridge filled with [molecular sieve 4A](#) and fitted it with a [small pump](#) (repurposed from a mattress inflator). This system actively recirculates the chamber atmosphere through the desiccant material. The cartridge includes perforations at the base and a sealed top with the pump connected, creating a directional flow that maximizes humidity absorption. With this system, we achieve a rapid drop in RH—from ~15% to below 3% in under an hour—and stable operation at ~3% RH even during continuous use.

- Bubbler Modification with Silica Gel Funnel:** We further modified the pressure regulator bubbler by attaching a funnel filled with silica gel pellets to its outlet. The funnel narrow end is sealed using masking tape perforated with small holes. This configuration ensures that the silica gel pellets remain contained while allowing gas to flow freely, preventing the desiccant from falling into the water of the pressure regulator's bubbler. While molecular sieves could also have been used, we opted for silica gel due to its built-in color indicator, which provides a convenient visual cue for when the material needs to be regenerated through thermal cycling. By forcing all exhaust gas to pass through this desiccant, the modification effectively prevents the bubbler from acting as a continuous source of humidity, thereby improving the long-term atmospheric stability of the chamber.

These two modifications transform the chamber from a biology-oriented anaerobic workstation into a humidity-stable environment suitable for advanced materials science applications. This approach is low-cost, easy to implement, and compatible with the existing infrastructure of the chamber described in our 2020 publication.

We hope this contribution proves useful to other laboratories working with air-sensitive materials in constrained environments.